

Incidence of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 in Drinking Water Sources in Zuru Zone of Kebbi State Nigeria

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Water Source is essential to human life, both for drinking, bathing and other domestic activities, which lead to discriminate demand and production of portable water in Kebbi State. Coliform such as *E. coli* O157:H7 is pathogenic serotype that is known to cause diarrheic diseases leading to fluid loss and other complication like haemolytic Uremic syndrome. A gram negative bacterium of the family Enterobacteriaceae, their presence in water signifies faecal contamination. A survey and antibiogram of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 in drinking water sources was investigated in Zuru zone of Kebbi State, Nigeria. One hundred water samples that include those from Borehole, (40) Well, (50) Tap (8) and Dam (2) were sampled for the study. The samples were inoculated onto MacConkey agar and pinkish colonies on the media were subculture on to Eosine Methylene Blue (EMB) agar. The presumptive *E. coli* isolated that appeared as green metallic sheen on EMB were further conformed biochemically. The people within the area do not consider water source as possible health hazards associated with such water. Therefore, wells stand the risk of contamination either from human beings or other animals as severally reported in the literature. The presence of Enterohaemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC) O157:H7 in Zuru town indicate the need for more intense public health awareness by their sanitary health officers and sources should be investigated periodically for their bacteriological quality.

Keywords: *E. coli* O157:H7, Microbiological water quality, Antibiogram, Drinking water.

INTRODUCTION

Before distributing to communities, potable water need to be sanitized and treated so as to be free from both chemical and microbial contamination Borehole and well water may also be free depending on the depth and site of the water. People resort to borehole and well water supply in the metropolis. The primary objective of some people within the area is to get water; they do not consider source and possible health hazards associated with such water sources. Therefore, wells stand the risk

of contamination either from human beings or other animals (Shahidullah *et al.*, 2000)

However, there has been mounting evidence that water is also a major vehicle for the transmission of diseases such as cholera, dysentery, typhoid, diarrhea, gastroenteritis, hepatitis, schistosomiasis, cancer, birth defects, liver and kidney damage (Hoboken *et al.*, 2004). It has been estimated that about 80% of the disease in developing countries such as Nigeria are waterborne; killing 25million people annually, 60% of whom are children as discovered by the Center for Diseases Control (World Health Organization 2024). Kebbi and Sokoto infant morbidity rates are suspected to be

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causally influenced by contaminated water sources.

Testing for the evidence of water contamination has been traditionally accomplished by the detection of total and faecal coli forms as disclosed by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (APHA, 2005) and many researchers have shown that the etiologic agents of these water borne diseases have a positive correlation with total and faecal coliforms in water bodies. Thus, this study laid emphasis on the coliform especially *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 because the presence of coliform bacteria in drinking water has been seen as an indication of faecal contamination and that indicate the possible presence of these pathogenic microorganisms since they also live in human and animal digestive systems (World Health Organization, 2022). This study is aimed at isolation and identification of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 in drinking water sources in areas of Zuru Emirates, Kebbi state, Nigeria using both cultural, phenotypic, biochemical and molecular techniques. The study also quantify the pathogen (*Escherichia coli* O157:H7) in the ra water sources.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area.

Zuru which is also about 240 kilometres away from Birnin Kebbi, is located in the southern part of the state, and is the headquarters of Zuru Emirate as well as Zuru Local Government Area. The major inhabitants, the Dakarkari are said to be the descendants of Achipawa from the Kiswa dynasty who migrated from somewhere in present day Saudi Arabia (Government of Kebbi State, 2007) (Batagarawa, 2011). The National Populations Commission, (2014) put its estimated population at 81,557 persons (National Population Commission, 2006).

Study design and Samples Collection

Cross sectional study was carried out using Random sampling in which 100 water samples were collected from four sampling frames of the Zuru zone between January 2020 to December 2021. The sampling units collected include water from Boreholes (40), Tap (8), Wells (50) and Dams (2). The samples were collected in a 250mls bottle and transported on packed box to Microbiology laboratory, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine for analysis. The water samples were collected according to the method described by the American Public Health Association (World Health Organization, 2024) and the world Health Organization (WHO) (APHA, 2005). Briefly, the samples were collected using sterile 250mls dark brown bottle for Boreholes, well, tap, and Dam water

samples, The entire samples collected were transported to the laboratory for the analysis within 2 to 3 hours of collection. The sample bottle was shaken vigorously for at least 20 times to obtain a uniform distribution of microorganisms as described (Monica, 2006).

Well water

The sample bottle will be tied with ropes around the necks. At the point of collection, the caps of the bottles will be removed and bottles lowered down the wells with the aid of the sterile ropes. When water filled the bottles, they were then be pulled from the wells and then covered (Yilmaz and Koc, 2014).

Borehole Water

Sample will be collected after operating the hand for some 2 minutes and sterilizing the mouth of the pump.

Dam Water

At specific sites especially where human activity with water is high, the sampling bottles will be inserted into the damp filled with the water and replace the cork back.

Tap water

the nozzle of the tap will be first removed and sterilized with a cotton wool soaked with methylated spirit and allow to cool by running the water for a few seconds 250mls sample bottles will be filled from a gentle flow of water and the 8 cap will be replaced carefully and labeled appropriately.

Determination of Physicochemical Parameters

Temperature

Temperature of the Drinking water sources were determined in field by inserting a Mercury-in-glass thermometer (N2-Field England made Brannon Model) into the sample until when the mercury level become constant then the temperature of the water were recorded (Atikson *et al.*, (2012)

Determination of pH

P^H values were measured using a P^H meter. The P^H meter was calibrated before taking P^H measurements. For calibration standard buffers of P^H 4.00, 7.00 and 10.00 are used. P^H of water indicates the hydrogen ion concentration in water. The concept of P^H was put forward by Sorenson in 1909. It is expressed as the

Figure 1.1: Steps in Isolation and identification of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7.

logarithm of the reciprocal of the hydrogen ion concentration in moles/litre at a given temperature. While the alkalinity or acidity measures the total resistance to the P^H change or buffering capacity, the P^H gives the hydrogen ion activity. The P^H scale extends from 0 (very acidic) to 14 (very alkaline) with 7 corresponding to exact neutrality at 25°C (Peter *et al.*, 2020).

Determination of Turbidity

The magnitude of the suspended solids in the sample were assessed visually by comparing clarity with that of distilled water and simply categorized as clear (C), lightly turbid (LT) or highly turbid (HT) as demonstrated by (Udoma, 2014)

Electrical conductivity:

Electrical conductivity (EC) is a measure of how conductive the water is to electrical current. The greater the ion concentration, greater is the EC. Generally, higher the EC, higher is the total dissolved solids. Electrical Conductivity is an indirect measure for finding the total dissolved solids in a water body. To convert the electrical conductivity of a water sample (micro Siemens per cm, $\mu S/cm$) to the concentration of total dissolved solids (ppm), the conductivity must be multiplied by a factor between 0.46 and 0.9 (depending on the unique mixture

of the dissolved materials). A widely accepted conversion factor is 0.67. $TDS (ppm) = Conductivity \{(\mu S/cm) \times 0.67\}$. The instrument used for measuring conductivity is conductivity meter (Bello *et al.*, 2013).

Isolation, Identification and Antibiogram

Escherichia coli O157: H7 from water sources in Argungu zone, Kebbi State were isolated using standard cultural techniques followed by enumeration of aerobic mesophilic bacteria on the basis of MPN//100mL and identification using phenotypic and biochemical characterizations according to the procedures described (Monica, 2006, Peter *et al.*, 2020, Bello *et al.*, 2013 and Aliyu *et al.*, 2018). Antibiotic profiling of isolates were carried out using disc diffusion technique according to Kirby Bearer, and interpreted according to Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute (Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute, 2017, 2018 and 2020) standards.

Confirmation of the isolates using Molecular Analysis

DNA Extraction and Polymere Chain Reaction (PCR)

These were carried out using Qiagen DNA extraction Kit as describe by (Fagan *et al.*, 2011). Multiplex PCR amplifications were carried out using Qiagen Hot Start[®] master mix.

Table 1: Information of Primers used for amplification of stx genes in *E. coli* isolated in the study

Oligonucleotides sequence (5'–3')	Specificity
F-CAACACTGGATGATCTCAG R-CCCCCTCAACTGCTAATA	Shiga toxin type 1
F-ATCAGTCGTCACACTGGT R-CTGCTGCTGTACAGTGACAAA	Shiga toxin type 2

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of Borehole Water from Zuru in Kebbi State.

Sampling frame	No of samples collected	Mean values of the tested parameters + SD					
Zuru Town	16	6.8	26	8.3	2.05	0.74	16
Fakai	4	0.4±00	0.4±79	3. ±8±	1.41±00	0.29±0	8
		6.8	26	7.27	1.50	0.68	19
		0.4±00	0.5±00	0.4±21	0.36±7	0.16±5	41.5±30
Sakaba	4	6.4	26	18.76	5.85	1.25	17
		0.44±3	1.00±0	7.74±2	2.57±4	0.72±9	14.67±5
Wasagu	16	6.5	26	10.17	2.73	0.86	15
		0.4±1	0.4±7	6.19±3	2.2±01	0.4±13	1.9±00

The following components were mixed together on ice.

Qiagen mastermix	12.5µl
Forward primer	1 µl
Reverse primer	1 µl
DNA template	5 µl
Nuclease free water	<u>5.5 µl</u> 25 µl

The PCR Protocols are as follows

Initial denaturation	94°C for 180 seconds
Denaturation	94°C for 30 seconds
Annealing	55°C for 30 seconds
Extension	78°C for 60 seconds
Final extension	78°C 300 seconds

Agarose gel electrophoresis were used to identify the positive pathotype and the size of amplicons were determine by comparing with 100-bp DNA ladder (Master cycler personal Eppendorf Germany (Paton and Paton, 2002).

Primers Used in the study

Primers specific for *E. coli* stx genes were used in this study, the primer sequences are presented in the table below;

RESULTS

Physicochemical properties of drinking water sources from Zuru Emirate in Kebbi State were carried out; the

parameters studies were Temperature, P^H, Biological Oxygen Demand, Dissolve Oxygen and Electric Conductivity. The result of physicochemical properties of borehole water from Zuru zone in Kebbi State shows that, the minimum value of P^H obtained were 6.4 (0.44±3) in Sakaba of Zuru zone while the maximum value was 7.7 (0.22±2) (Table 1). Temperature had the minimum of 26.0°C with mean (0.4.4±79) while the maximum were 26.56°C (0.81±4) were recorded in Zuru zone (Table 2). Dissolved oxygen had the minimum of 4.45mg/l (3.12±0) and 14.01mg/l (8.06±8) as the highest valued obtained. The result of biological oxygen demand shows the minimum of 1.50mg²/L (0.42±4) while the maximum value of 5.85mg²/L, was obtained for Biological oxygen Demand. So also the electric conductivity result recorded were 15.8µs/cm as the lowest value will the maximum were 19.00µs/cm.

The results of physicochemical properties of Dam Water from Kebbi State had the lowest P^H of 6.0 (0.44±1) in Zuru zone and maximum of 7.2 (0.22±2) in Sakaba from Zuru zone. Temperature of 26°C (0.8±6) as the minimum value while the maximum value was 27°C (0.8±34). Dissolve oxygen had lowest value of 6.9mg/L (0.46±5) from Zuru town and maximum value of 22.0mg/L (7.72±2) Zuru likewise Biological oxygen demand had 0.9mg₂/L (0.5±1) from Fakai as lowest value while 7.28mg/L (0.3±1) in Wasagu as the maximum value recorded. Turbidity had the lowest value of 0.41mg/L (0.96±1) from Sakaba and highest value of 1.70mg/L (0.62±1) in Zuru town. Electric conductivity had 1.4µscm

Table 2. Physicochemical Properties of Well Water from Zuru zone in Kebbi State (Mean \pm SD).

Sampling frame	No of samples collected	pH	Temp °C	DO mgL ⁻¹	BOD mgL ⁻¹	Turbidity mgL ⁻¹	EC μ S/cm
Zuru Town	15	7 0.16 \pm 3	27 0.8 \pm 34	7.1 0.4 \pm 20	1.9 0.51 \pm 4	0.89 0.3 \pm 1	16 64.2 \pm 00
Fakai	10	6.4 0.16 \pm 3	26.5 0.81 \pm 3	11 8.32 \pm 2	3.3 2.6 \pm 2	0.87 0.58 \pm 2	14 10.36 \pm 4
Sakaba	10	6.0 0.4 \pm 4	27 0.8 \pm 34	22 2.2 \pm 01	7.2 8.2 \pm 4	1.7 0.57 \pm 2	0.45 0.68 \pm 00
Wasagu	15	6.4 0.163	26 0.61 \pm 1	6.16 0.4 \pm 10	2.19 1.8 \pm 3	0.43 0.18 \pm 2	18 79.4 \pm 0

Table 3. Physicochemical Properties of Dam Water from Zuru zone in Kebbi State (Mean \pm SD)

Sampling frame	No of samples collected	pH	Temp °C	DO mgL ⁻¹	BOD mgL ⁻¹	Turbidity mgL ⁻¹	EC μ S/cm
Zuru Town	1	7.2 0.22 \pm 2	27 0.8 \pm 8	6.9 0.46 \pm 5	1.8 0.05 \pm 0	0.84 0.4 \pm 1	2.4 2.2 \pm 0
Fakai	1	6.8 0.50 \pm 7	26 0.81 \pm 6	7.26 0.42 \pm 6	1.7 0.05 \pm 0	0.6 0.4 \pm 4	19 1.02 \pm 5
Sakaba	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wasagu	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4. Physicochemical Properties of Tap Water from Zuru zone in Kebbi State.

Sampling frame	No of samples collected	pH	Temp °C	DO mgL ⁻¹	BOD mgL ⁻¹	Turbidity mgL ⁻¹	EC μ S/cm
Zuru Town	1	7.2 0.22 \pm 2	27 0.8 \pm 8	7.6 0.4 \pm 21	1.8 0.1 \pm 00	10.0 0.5 \pm 2	1.2 1.05 \pm 2
Fakai	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sakaba	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wasagu	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

(0.72 \pm 09) from Fakai as the lowest value recorded and 2.6 μ S/cm (0.3 \pm 6) as the maximum value, the results were presented.

Shows the results of physicochemical properties of Tap water, P^H had the lowest value of 6.8(0.50 \pm 7) from Zuru and maximum while the highest value of 7.2 (0.22 \pm 2). Biological oxygen demand had 1.6mg/0₂/L (0.04 \pm 0) and maximum value of 1.8mg/0₂/L (0.1 \pm 00) in zuru town, Temperature 26.0°C (0.44 \pm 0) as lowest value and 27°C (0.8 \pm 8) as the highest value. Dissolve oxygen had 1.8mg/L (0.05 \pm 0) from Zuru and highest value recorded was 7.6mg/l (0.4 \pm 21) and Turbidity 1.0mg/L (0.53 \pm 2) as lowest value and 8.4mg/L as highest value of (4.48 \pm 1), Electric conductivity had 1.2 μ S/cm (1.05 \pm 2) as lowest value and highest value 9.4 μ S/cm (0.48 \pm 2) the results were presented.

The results of the aerobic mesophilic bacteria count

of drinking water samples from Zuru zone obtain from Borehole was 1.2 (5.39 \pm 9) as the lowest count from Zuru town and 2.3(6.28 \pm 2) as maximum from Wasagu, Tap had 1.8(3.54 \pm 4) as minimum count from Zuru town and 3.1 (9.0 \pm 00) as maximum from Wasagu. Dam had 2.06(6.35 \pm 8) as lowest count from Fakai as lowest count and 4.4 (4.22 \pm 00) as maximum from Wasagu, similarly, well had 1.8 (3.34 \pm 6) from Wasagu as lowest count and 2.2 (2.32 \pm 7) as maximum count recorded. The result is presented in Table 7

Antibiogram of *E coli* O157:H7 isolated from drinking water Sources in Zuru zone of Kebbi State that were subjected on a panel of nine {9} different antibiotic, seven proved susceptibility to antibiotic. The results were presented in Table 18, that indicated an overall clearance lower zone of inhibition of (32mm) and higher zone of inhibition of 36mm against Ciprofloxacin (67%) (24mm)

Table 5. Mean Bacterial count of drinking water samples from Zuru Zone

Sampling Location	BH	Sources TP AMB (cfu/ml)	DM	WW
ZuruTown	12 0.39±0	18 1.04±4	24 0.83±13	20 2.03±0
Fakai	20 14.3±3	22 0.82±04	26 1.20±02	18 0.24±04
Sakaba	19 5.37±4	28 2.05±6	28 1.9±3	22 2.08±02
Wasagu	24 2.28±2	30 2.00±00	44 4.02±00	18 2.34±06

Key: AMB – Aerobic Mesophilic Bacteria, BH – Borehole, TP – Tap, DM – Dam, WW – Well water.

Figure 1. Susceptibility profile of *E. coli*: O157:H7 isolated in Borehole from Zuru zone. The zones of inhibition (mm) > 4mm imply sensitivity (clearance).

Table 6. Confirmation of Stx₁, Stx₂ and H7 Gene on *E. coli* O157:H7 isolated from Drinking Water Source in Kebbi State.

Area	Sources	No. of Sample screen	No. of Isolates positive Stx ₁	No. of Isolates positive Stx ₂	No. of Isolates positive H7
Zuru	Borehole	40(4)	1	3	2
	Tap	8(1)	0	0	0
	Well Water	50(9)	2	3	3
	Dam	2(2)	0	0	0

against sulphamethoxazole (65%) erythromycin (20mm 65%) oxytetracycline (67%), Gentamycin (65%), Streptomycin (67%) and Neomycin (67%). All isolates proved ineffective to Amplicilin (67%) and Tetracycline (67%). The results were presented below.

Nine isolates showed band of Stx₂ and one Stx₁, eighteen (18) isolates from Zuru zone samples. Six(6) Stx₂ genes, and three 3 Stx₁ while five (5) H7 showed band. Out of the eighteen (18) isolates from zuru zone subjected to PCR amplification of H7 gene, 9 showed positive band of the

Figure 2: Gel image of H7 Amplicon on 1% Agarose Gel

Keys; Well 1 =100bp Ladder, Well 2 = Zuru Town (Borehole), Well 3 = Sakaba (Borehole), Well 4 =Sakaba (Tap Water), Well 5 = Wasagu(Tap Water), Well 6 = Fakai (Well), Well 7 =Zuru Town(Well Water), Well 8 = Fakai (Borehole), Well 9 = Zuru Town (Dam Water), Well 10 =Fakai (Dam Hole), Well 11 = Negative control and Well 12 =100bp Ladder

Figure 3: Gel image of Stx₁&Stx₂Amplicon on 1% Agarose

Keys; Well 1 = 100bp Ladder Well 2 = Wasagu (Stx₁) (Borehole), Well 3 = Fakai (Stx₁) (Borehole), Well 4 = Wasagu (Stx₂) (Well Water), Well 5 = Zuru Town (Stx₁) (Borehole), Well 6 = Fakai (Stx₁ & Stx₂) (Well water), Well 7 = Sakaba (Stx₁) (Dam Water), Well 8 = Zuru Town (Stx₁ & Stx₂) (Dam Water), Well 9 = Sakaba (Stx₁) (Borehole), Well 10 = Fakai (Stx₁) (Borehole), Well 11 = Zuru Town (Stx₁) (Tap Water) and Well 12 = Negative Control

expected amplicon using 1% agarose gel pre-stained with ethidium bromide.

The drinking water sources in Zuru zone of Kebbi state study for all its zones were examined and identified at every zone with the help of water board official addition to visual observation at every zone. Major drinking water sources were Dam, Well, Tap and Borehole as presented.

The results of the mean Bacterial aerobic count of drinking water samples from Zuru zone obtained ranged from 1–26, Fakai, (21.45±50), Sakaba (8.92±51), Wasagu (19.80±00) and Zuru town (20.25±00) for Borehole, 1-31, for well water Fakai (7.07±38), Sakaba (6.24±16), Wasagu (2.20±00) and Zuru town (3.44±31), Tap had 1-3 Fakai (7.25±00) not tested for Sakaba, Wasagu and Zuru town, while Dam had 1-8 (26.30±00) for Fakai, 50.20±6 for Sakaba, Wasagu and Sakaba were not tested. The total coliform count cfu/100m/e for Zuru town had 20.26±00, Fakai (1.58±75), Sakaba (58.36±3), and Wasagu (1.92±00) for Borehole, Fakai (1.53±15) for Tap, while Zuru town, Sakaba, and Wasagu were not tested for total coliform, Dam (1.22±08) is for Fakai and 3.36±46, Sakaba, Wasagu and Zuru town were not tested. Well water had (1.80±00) for Zuru town, (1.00±00) for Fakai, 1.00, for Sakaba and (1.22±08) for Wasagu. The result is presented in Table 7.

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Antibiogram of *E. coli* O157:H7 isolated from drinking water sources in Kebbi state that were subjected on a panel of nine {9} different antibiotics, seven proved susceptibility to antibiotic. The results were presented in Table 12, which indicated an overall clearance lower zone of inhibition of (32mm) and higher zone of inhibition of 36mm against Ciprofloxacin (67%) (24mm) against sulphamethoxazole (65%) erythromycin (20mm) 65% oxytetracycline 67%, Gentamycin (65%), Streptomycin (67%) and Neomycin (67%). All isolates proved ineffective

to Ampicillin (67%) and Tetracycline (67%)

All culture and Biochemical test positive isolates that were subjected for confirmation of Stx₁, Stx₂ & H7 genes of *E. coli* O157:H7 from drinking water sources in Kebbi state, out of thirteen (13) isolates from Argungu zone, Nine isolates showed band of Stx₂ and one Stx₁, eighteen (18) isolates from Zuru zone samples. Six (6) Stx₂ genes and three (3) Stx₁, while five (5) H7 showed band.

The Risk factor includes unsanitary seal of borehole, nearest to latrine, trees around borehole, pollution (rubbish and surface water discharge, poor drainage near the water point and abandoned material inside the well as presented in Table 14

CONCLUSION

Zuru Emirate of Kebbi state was found to depend mostly on well water followed by borehole water as their sources of drinking water. Surprisingly, some of the communities are still using raw dam water as their drinking water sources. Some drinking water sources in study area can be regarded as good based on their physicochemical properties, although slight pH adjustment may be required in some instances. Some sources including well water are not portable due to objectionable contamination with *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 many of which are resistant to some commonly used antibiotics.

Polymerase Chain Reaction was employed to ascertain the nature of genes involved in the pathogenicity or otherwise of the isolates. This study has provided information on the genetic profiling of *E. coli* O157:H7 in drinking water sources of Zuru Emirates. The findings of this work could also point to measures to be adopted for infective water disinfection strategy to supply portable water to the resident or communities so that water borne diseases could be prevented.

RECOMMENDATION

Separate water sources for animal and human consumption should be separated. Sufficient sanitary measures such as regular disinfection, bacteriological examination and inspection of drinking water sources and fencing all water sources, should be provided over spring water for human consumption. Based on the results obtained in this study, drinking water sources of Zuru zone in Kebbi state can be regarded as being fair based on the parameter under consideration, although need little improvements. However, further studies with reference to the physicochemical and antibiotics profiling of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 would have to be done time to time to have a broader picture of this study.

RECOMMENDATION

It is recommended that the pH of water from boreholes and taps should be regularly checked and adjusted before consumption. Similarly, availing separate water sources for animal and human consumption through fencing the water sources in order to prevent animals from contaminating water for human consumption would improve the quality of the drinking water Sources in the area. Authorities should strengthen efforts to provide portable drinking water by regular inspection, disinfection and bacteriological examination of the open drinking water sources in the study area. Furthermore, studies focusing on the prevailing antibiotic resistance genes of *E. coli* O157:H7 should be conducted in order to broaden the outcome of this study.

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